

Developing a Typology of Biodiversity Research: Methodological Framework

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Biodiversity research is inherently diverse in its scope, objectives, and methodological approaches, encompassing a wide range of disciplines, from ecology, taxonomy, genetics to social sciences, economics, and policy studies. This reflects the complex and interconnected nature of biodiversity systems at different levels of biological organisation, from genes to ecosystems, but also the socio-environmental dynamics pertinent to biodiversity conservation. In addition, the production of biodiversity data and knowledge involves a variety of stakeholders such as academic institutions, governmental agencies, or non-governmental organisations, each contributing distinct perspectives and expertise. While representing a major strength of the field, this diversity also presents challenges for systematically describing, comparing, and analysing research activities across domains.

Differences in terminology, thematic focus, and methodological approaches across disciplines and institutions can make it difficult to obtain a coherent overview of research activities and, as a result, to assess how efforts are distributed across topics and priorities. In this context, the development of a standardised typology is essential to establish a shared reference framework that enables consistent classification and interpretation of research activities. Controlled vocabularies provide an effective means of addressing these challenges by promoting consistency. The use of standardised terms enhances the discoverability and interoperability of data, making it easier for users to identify, access and reuse relevant information. In addition, controlled vocabularies offer clear and agreed-upon definitions for each term, which supports the consistent and precise use of language across research communities. This leads to improved data quality, facilitates communication among stakeholders, and strengthens the reliability of research classification and analysis (Buschbom *et al.*, 2024; Jagannathan K. *et al.*, 2023).

The development of such a typology was initiated in 2022 by the Belgian Biodiversity Platform as part of the *Conservation Research Matters* initiative. This effort aimed to improve the strategic understanding of Belgian biodiversity research activities by establishing a structured approach to their classification. Within this context, typology was conceived as a key tool to support the systematic mapping and analysis of conservation-related research efforts. Since its inception, the development process has involved iterative refinement and consultation with the research community to ensure its relevance and applicability across the biodiversity research landscape.

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Objective

The typology aims at providing the Belgian Biodiversity Platform with a structured and transparent framework for classifying biodiversity research activities across disciplines. By establishing a common language and a standardised set of categories, it enhances the consistency and comparability of information to perform more robust analyses of the biodiversity research landscape. Such standardisation is a necessary step to further support the systematic mapping of research activities, facilitate the identification of trends, gaps, overlaps, and potential complementarities. Importantly as regard to the mission and values of the Belgian Biodiversity Platform, it improves the evidence base for strategic planning and policy development.

Scope

Designed to encompass a broad range of biodiversity research activities, including fundamental, applied, and policy-relevant research, the typology covers research conducted in Belgium by academic institutions, governmental bodies, research institutes, and non-governmental organisations. It captures the diversity of research topics, methodological approaches and thematic priorities, while remaining sufficiently flexible to accommodate emerging fields and evolving research agendas. This is primarily intended to support the analysis over time of biodiversity research at national and regional levels.

Application of the Typology in the Biodiversity Expertise Registry

The use of this kind of typology supports resource allocation, fosters coordination among scientific, policy, and funding communities. Ultimately, it aims to increase the coherence, visibility, and strategic value of biodiversity research, contributing to more effective responses to biodiversity challenges.

As such, the typology developed by the Belgian Biodiversity Platform has been used as the structural backbone for the development of its Biodiversity Expertise Registry. It provides the conceptual and organisational framework for describing and categorising the expertise of researchers and institutions active in biodiversity-related fields. By serving as the underlying classification structure, it enables the consistent annotation of expertise profiles, research topics, and thematic domains, thereby facilitating the systematic organisation and retrieval of information. The use of the typology in the registry has also provided an opportunity to test and refine its categories through practical application, ensuring that it remains relevant, usable, and responsive to the needs of biodiversity research, policy and practice communities.

Methodological Approach to Typology Development

Step 1. Identification and Analysis of Key Reference Documents

The development of typology began with the identification and review of key reference documents relevant to biodiversity and conservation. These included national and international research strategies, policy frameworks and agendas related to biodiversity science and policy such as the COP15 report on the Global Biodiversity Framework (2022), the IPBES Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services (2019), the European Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (2020) and the Belgian Biodiversity Strategy (2013). The objective of this step was to identify commonly used thematic domains, terminologies, and structural approaches that could inform the initial design of the typology. The analysis of these documents provided the conceptual foundation for the subsequent identification of research topics.

Step 2. Research Topics Identification and Categorisation

Based on the analysis of reference materials, an initial list of research topics was compiled. Topics were identified through the systematic extraction of thematic areas and keywords commonly used to describe biodiversity research activities. These topics were then organised into a preliminary hierarchical structure, grouping related research areas under 17 broad thematic categories. The aim of this step was to create a structured overview that captured the diversity of biodiversity research while maintaining a level of organisation that would allow for meaningful classification and analysis.

Step 3. Refinement with Subtopics

Following the identification of the main research topics, further refinement was undertaken through the introduction of subtopics. This step aimed to increase the granularity of the typology and to better reflect the diversity and specificity of research activities within each thematic area. 150 subtopics were developed iteratively, ensuring that each represented a distinct research focus while remaining logically connected to its corresponding higher-level topic. This hierarchical structuring allowed the typology to accommodate both broad thematic analyses and more detailed classifications of research activities.

Step 4. Expert Consultation via a Survey

To ensure the relevance and usability of the typology, an expert consultation was conducted through a structured survey targeting the Belgian research community at large. This participatory approach ensured that the typology was both comprehensive and aligned with real-world research topics in Belgium. The selection of participants was based on a systematic review of Belgian universities and research institutions. 450 Research units were invited to review the proposed topics and subtopics, assess their clarity and completeness, and suggest additions or modifications where necessary. This consultation step enabled the incorporation of expert knowledge and practical experience, helping to validate the conceptual structure and ensure that the typology reflected the realities of biodiversity research practice.

Step 5. Data Analysis and Typology Adjustment

The responses collected through the expert survey were systematically analysed to identify patterns, synonymies, and suggested improvements. Based on this analysis, adjustments were made to the structure of the typology, including the modification, merging, or addition of topics where necessary. This step contributed to improving the robustness and usability of the typology while ensuring that it remained grounded in stakeholder input.

Step 6. Definition of Each Topic

Following the structural refinement of the typology, clear and consistent definitions were developed for each topic and subtopic to establish a shared understanding of the scope and meaning of each category, thereby reducing ambiguity and supporting consistent classification across users and contexts. In parallel, the development of these definitions enabled the creation of a comprehensive glossary, compiling the terminology associated with the typology and providing standardised descriptions of key concepts. The glossary serves as a reference tool to support interpretation and application of the typology, ensuring transparency and facilitating consistent use across different users and institutions. Wherever possible, definitions were aligned with terminology from recognised scientific and policy frameworks to promote interoperability and conceptual clarity.

Step 7. Review and Updates

Recognising that biodiversity research is a dynamic and evolving field, the typology was designed to undergo periodic review and updating. This step involves revisiting the structure and content of the typology in light of emerging research areas, changes in research and policy priorities, and suggested updates feedback from the research community. Regular updates help maintain the relevance and applicability of the typology over time and ensure that it continues to support accurate analyses of the biodiversity research landscape. The review process also provides opportunities to improve usability and address identified limitations.

Transferability of the Typology Approach

The development of this typology was not intended to produce an exhaustive inventory of all possible biodiversity research topics. It reflects the structure and priorities of the current Belgian biodiversity research landscape. The typology was designed to capture the most relevant and representative areas of research activity, while maintaining sufficient flexibility to accommodate future developments and emerging themes. By grounding its structure in observed research practices and stakeholder input, the typology aims to provide a realistic and usable framework aligned with the national context.

At the same time, the methodological approach adopted for the development of this typology has value beyond the Belgian context. The principles of structured topic identification, stakeholder consultation, and iterative refinement can be applied to other national or thematic research landscapes. This approach is not limited to biodiversity research and may serve as a useful model for describing and analysing research activities in other scientific domains. By promoting standardised and transparent classification practices, such approaches contribute

to improved comparability, strategic analysis, and evidence-based decision-making across research fields.

The typology of biodiversity research is periodically updated. The latest version is available through the link provided in *Annex 1*.

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ANNEX 1. The topics

The latest version of the typology is available for download in CSV format at the following link: **10.5281/zenodo.21129146**.

ANNEX 2. The Glossary

A glossary describing the topics included in the typology is currently being finalised and will be made available in a forthcoming version of this document.